

Erasmus+ Programme

Key Action 2 - Cooperation Partnerships in School Education

REPORT

R5.2.2

Educator Training Programme Pilot

Co-funded by
the European Union

A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education

Grant Agreement No. 2022-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000090043

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Short Description	This document presents the results of the piloting of the ASAP Educator Training Programme carried out within the Erasmus+ ASAP project in five partner countries (Croatia, Czechia, Italy, Portugal and Slovenia). It documents training formats, implementation contexts, participant profiles and feedback collected from educators involved in the pilots. The report analyses strengths, challenges and adaptations of the Training Programme and provides consolidated insights to support its refinement, scalability and long-term use in school education contexts.

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Executive Summary

This report presents the results of the piloting of the ASAP Educator Training Programme carried out between May 2024 and June 2025 in Croatia, Czech Republic, Italy, Slovenia, and Portugal. The piloting aimed to validate the clarity, relevance, and practical applicability of the educator training component designed under WP5, as well as to assess how effectively teachers and educators could implement selected ASAP learning activities with preadolescents, parents, and colleagues.

Across all partner countries, the ASAP Programme proved to be highly relevant and adaptable. Training sessions—delivered in online, in-person, and hybrid formats—reached more than 100 external teachers, over 40 staff members, and hundreds of students, with Italy and Slovenia showing particularly large-scale implementation. Despite differences in timelines, school structures, and available resources, teachers consistently reported that the activities were clear, well-structured, and directly applicable to the challenges they face in classrooms, especially those related to online behaviour, emotional regulation, communication, and cyberbullying.

A notable strength across all pilots was the programme’s pedagogical design, which combines metacognitive strategies with practical, discussion-based activities. Pupils showed high engagement, openly sharing experiences related to digital life, while teachers valued the programme’s flexibility and its ability to generate authentic dialogue. Local adaptations—such as translations, contextual examples, shorter activity formats, and simplified instructions—further enhanced usability.

Challenges experienced across countries included limited time at the end of the school year, variable educator familiarity with reflective pedagogy, and reduced opportunities for parent engagement. Nevertheless, all countries met or exceeded their KPI targets and provided rich feedback to guide programme refinement.

The piloting confirms that the ASAP Educator Training Programme is a robust, scalable, and impactful tool for supporting European educators in guiding preadolescents toward safer, more reflective, and more responsible engagement with digital and social media environments.

Introduction

The ASAP project – *A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education* – was conceived to address one of the most urgent and complex challenges faced by European schools: how to support preadolescents, their families, and educators in navigating digital and social media environments safely, critically, and with a deeper understanding of the cognitive processes that influence online behaviour. Drawing on the priorities of the Erasmus+ Programme, the project places metacognition and the Learning-to-Learn Key Competence at the centre of digital education. Rather than limiting itself to risk-prevention approaches, ASAP promotes a reflective, transdisciplinary, and learning-oriented framework that helps the school community understand not only *what* young people do online, but *how* they think, evaluate, and decide when engaging with digital media.

Over the course of the project, ASAP partners jointly produced a significant body of research (WP2), developed an Educational Model and Programme grounded in metacognition (WP3), and validated this programme through extensive piloting activities with students, parents, teachers, and school leaders in five partner countries (WP4). The educator dimension – formalised and expanded in WP5 – completes this framework by addressing the professional development needs of teachers and educators. It acknowledges the growing complexity of the teaching profession and its central role in fostering safe, responsible, and critical engagement with social media among preadolescents. As highlighted in the application, teachers across the EU increasingly require updated, research-based training to keep pace with digital transformations, cognitive development insights, and emerging online risks.

The ASAP Educator Training Programme (WP5) responds directly to these needs. Designed by ProEduca with contributions from all partners, it translates the theoretical premises of the ASAP Educational Programme into a structured professional development path. It outlines the profile of the “ASAP Educator” – a figure grounded in the DigiCompEdu framework, equipped with competences in critical digital literacy, online safety, metacognition, and transdisciplinary thinking. The Programme prepares teachers to meaningfully integrate the ASAP activities into their school contexts and to guide students, parents, and colleagues through reflective learning processes related to digital media.

The piloting phase of the Educator Training Programme (A5.2) took place between May 2024 and June 2025 across Italy, Portugal, Slovenia, Croatia and the Czech Republic. In each country, partners conducted at least one pilot for internal staff and one for external teachers or educators. In line with the project design, the pilot consisted of a training session followed by a practical implementation period during which participants carried out selected ASAP activities with their own target groups. This cycle provided valuable insight into the usability, clarity, and transferability of the training materials, as well as the adaptability of the ASAP approach to diverse educational contexts. It also enabled the refinement of both methodology and pedagogical tools based on real-world experiences.

Across all countries, partners reported strong interest among educators, reflecting a clear need for structured support in digital/social media literacy, the prevention of cyberbullying and online risks, and the development of metacognitive learning strategies. Despite differences in school systems and local priorities, the pilot activities revealed several shared challenges: limited time in school schedules, varying levels of teacher familiarity with reflective pedagogies, and differing levels of parental engagement. At the same time, all pilots demonstrated the simplicity and flexibility of the ASAP activities, enabling teachers to integrate them into daily practice, adapt them to different age groups, and use them to stimulate meaningful dialogues with students and families.

The present Final Piloting Report brings together the results from all national pilots carried out within WP5. It provides:

- an overview of how the training was organised and delivered in each country;
- the number and profile of educators involved;
- a description of how selected learning activities were implemented with preadolescents, parents, and teachers;
- local adaptations and methodological adjustments;
- monitoring procedures and follow-up mechanisms;
- shared insights, emerging trends, and challenges observed across countries.

This report contributes directly to WP5 objectives. It supports the refinement of the ASAP Educator Training Programme for long-term use, informs the creation of future training pathways, and strengthens the foundation for the project's sustainability and legacy activities under WP7. Ultimately, the piloting confirms that the ASAP approach—rooted in metacognition, transdisciplinarity, and digital awareness—offers a relevant, practical, and innovative response to the evolving needs of European schools as they face the complex reality of digital and social media in preadolescence.

1. Croatia

1.1 General Introduction to the National Pilot

The Croatian piloting of the ASAP Educator Training Programme was carried out by **DKMK – Društvo za komunikacijsku i medijsku kulturu**, a well-established organisation with extensive experience in media education, teacher training, and digital wellbeing. The national pilot consisted of two complementary components:

1. **External Pilot with 25 primary school teachers** from 25 different schools across Croatia.
2. **Internal Pilot with 15 DKMK trainers/educators** to strengthen internal capacity and harmonise future implementation.

Together, these two components created a coherent piloting process that tested the ASAP methodology in real classroom environments and prepared DKMK's internal team for long-term programme delivery.

The overarching goal of the Croatian pilot was to validate the ASAP Educator Training Programme within the Croatian context, test representative activities from all Learning Units (LUs), and gather feedback from participants to refine and localise the programme.

1.2. Number and Profile of Participants

External Pilot

- 25 teachers (22 female; 3 male)
- Representing 25 different primary schools across Croatia
- Subjects included: Croatian language, class teaching, ICT, social sciences, arts, and special education
- Participants came from both urban and rural schools, ensuring wide national coverage

Internal Pilot

- 15 DKMK trainers (14 female; 1 male)
- All with extensive experience in media literacy, digital safety, and educational programme delivery

Organisations involved

- Primary schools from across Croatia
- DKMK (implementing partner)
- No additional associated partners were required

1.3. Location and Format of Pilots

The external pilot in Croatia was delivered in person on 24–25 February 2025 at a central training venue arranged by DKMK. It took the form of a group training that combined presentations, hands-on practice, and guided reflection, giving participants the opportunity to work through selected activities together. The internal pilot was also delivered face to face as a one-day workshop at the DKMK offices, focused on professional exchange, team learning, and methodological alignment. Both pilots relied on an interactive, in-person format that encouraged collaborative learning and allowed educators to test activities in real time, strengthening their understanding of the programme before wider implementation.

1.4. Main Goals and Objectives

The Croatian pilot focused on several interconnected objectives. It introduced teachers and DKMK staff to the ASAP educational philosophy and pedagogical approach, while creating a space to test selected activities from each Learning Unit in a teacher-training context. A central aim was to strengthen teachers' competences in digital wellbeing, media literacy, online risk prevention, and reflective teaching. Throughout the pilot, the team collected both qualitative and quantitative feedback to support further refinement of the training programme. The process also served to prepare DKMK's internal team for future dissemination and mentoring roles. To ensure national relevance, terminology, examples, and discussion prompts were adapted to reflect the Croatian educational environment and the digital experiences of local pupils.

1.5. Pilot Implementation

All Learning Units from the ASAP Educational Programme were presented during the Croatian pilot. From each unit, three representative activities were selected according to their suitability for adult training, the clarity of their structure, their relevance to Croatian schools, and their ability to offer a balanced combination of theoretical input and practical engagement. Through this selection, teachers were introduced to activities addressing emotions and emotional regulation in digital environments, communication skills and common online misunderstandings, authenticity and self-expression, critical questioning and reflective thinking, as well as Onlife behaviours and issues related to online identity.

The sequence and duration of the pilot created a comprehensive learning flow. The external pilot took place over two full days and included a complete introduction to the ASAP methodology, hands-on testing of the selected activities, and structured reflection supported by moderated group discussions. The internal pilot was designed as a one-day workshop devoted to reviewing all Learning Units, reflecting on the training methodology, and planning future mentoring and implementation support. This structure enabled participants to engage with the programme both as learners experiencing the activities and as educators analysing their pedagogical logic, thereby deepening their understanding of how the approach translates into classroom practice.

1.6. Changes and Context-Specific Adaptations

Several adaptations were introduced to ensure that the programme fitted well within the Croatian educational context. Key terminology, examples, and online scenarios were translated and contextualised, and relevant Croatian media cases were incorporated to make the activities more relatable for participants. The timing of selected exercises was adjusted to fit the 45–90-minute segments typical of teacher training sessions, while additional reflection moments were added to help teachers connect the content to the everyday challenges they observe in their classrooms. Examples were also adapted for pupils aged 10–14, reflecting the digital habits and experiences common in Croatian schools. These adjustments contributed to strong engagement throughout the pilot and ensured that the content aligned with local practice and teacher expectations.

1.7. Challenges Encountered

The Croatian pilot proceeded smoothly and encountered only minor logistical difficulties. The main challenges related to managing the tight schedules of teachers participating in a two-day training, as well as differences in digital competence and levels of experience with reflective methodologies. Balancing the theoretical and practical components within a limited timeframe required careful facilitation, and the team also needed to ensure that participants fully understood activities originally developed in English—a challenge resolved through timely translations. Thanks to DKMK's extensive

experience with educational programmes, these issues were addressed effectively, allowing the pilot to run successfully and achieve its intended outcomes.

1.8. Feedback Collection and Key Findings

How Feedback Was Collected

- Online evaluation forms
- Short written reflections
- Group discussions during training

Main Feedback Themes

Teachers reported that:

- the training was **highly relevant**, practical, and immediately applicable;
- the activities were clearly structured and easy to integrate into lessons;
- the mix of theory and hands-on practice was well balanced;
- reflective dialogue helped them better understand digital challenges faced by pupils;
- they valued the opportunity to exchange experiences with colleagues from different regions.

Internal trainers highlighted:

- the usefulness of methodological alignment;
- the importance of mentoring structures;
- the need for easy-to-share activity summaries for future dissemination.

Quantitative feedback was exceptionally high (average ratings above 5.8/6 in all categories).

1.9. Conclusions, Lessons Learned, and Recommendations

The Croatian national pilot successfully validated both the **content** and the **methodology** of the ASAP Educator Training Programme. The training format worked effectively, and participants demonstrated strong motivation to integrate the activities into their teaching practice.

Key Takeaways

- Teachers value structured, practical activities that address real digital challenges.
- Reflective discussions are essential for deeper understanding and teacher engagement.
- Translated materials and context-specific examples significantly increase relevance.
- Internal team alignment strengthens future delivery quality.

Suggestions for Improvement

Educational Programme:

- provide even shorter, simplified versions of some activities;
- include additional localised examples and case studies;
- expand resources on real-life online conflicts and prevention strategies.

Educator Training Programme:

- offer optional follow-up sessions or online mentoring;
- provide ready-to-use implementation guides for teachers;
- introduce a modular structure for schools with limited time.

2. Czech Republic

2.1. General Introduction to the National Pilot

The national piloting of the ASAP Educator Training Programme in the Czech Republic was implemented by ProEduca, an organisation specialising in youth education, digital literacy, and school–community support. The pilot consisted of two core components:

- External pilot with teachers from two primary schools.
- Internal pilot with ProEduca staff to harmonise understanding of the ASAP methodology.

The overall goal of the pilot was to introduce teachers to selected Learning Units (LUs), test practical activities, explore classroom applicability, and gather insights for improving the educational programme.

The Czech pilot focused strongly on digital wellbeing, online emotions, communication, and social-media-related challenges—topics highly relevant to local schools.

2.2. Number and Profile of Participants

External Pilot (Teachers)

- 16 teachers total
 - ZŠ Dobrá Voda: **11 teachers**
 - ZŠ Do Života Benátky: **5 teachers**
- Subjects represented: Czech language, humanities, ICT, primary education, counselling, classroom leadership
- KPI target: 15 → achieved (+1)
- Teachers worked mainly with pupils aged 11–14

Internal Pilot (ProEduca Staff)

- 5 staff members, responsible for programme delivery and internal alignment
- KPI target: 5 → fully achieved

2.3. Organisations Involved

- ProEduca – national implementing partner
- ZŠ Dobrá Voda (České Budějovice) – innovative and digitally oriented school
- ZŠ Do Života Benátky – school focused on practical, modern learning methods

Both schools participated voluntarily and showed strong interest in the ASAP approach.

2.4. Location and Format of Pilots

The external pilot was delivered directly on-site in participating schools, where trainers worked with teachers during short training blocks integrated into regular pedagogical meetings, followed by the implementation of activities in standard classroom lessons. This phase also included subsequent communication with teachers and systematic reporting. In parallel, the internal pilot was carried out both online and in person and focused primarily on aligning the methodology across partners, preparing the implementation teams, and reviewing the Learning Units before they were tested

externally. All training and implementation activities in both pilots took place between May and June 2025. The condensed timeline was largely shaped by end-of-year school calendars, which influenced the availability of teachers and the scheduling of sessions.

2.5. Main Goals and Objectives

The Czech pilot aimed to familiarise teachers with the ASAP methodology, its structure, and the selected Learning Units, and to test a set of activities focused on emotions, communication, and online behaviour. Its purpose was also to support teachers in developing strategies that strengthen pupils' digital resilience and to gather feedback on the feasibility, clarity, and usability of the materials. A further objective was to reinforce the internal capacity of participating educators and institutions to implement and disseminate the programme more broadly in the future.

2.6. Pilot Implementation

Content and Learning Units Used

Because of time constraints, teachers worked with a carefully chosen set of activities drawn from four Learning Units. The Emotions unit focused on helping pupils identify the feelings hidden behind online messages, while the Communication unit explored misunderstandings that often arise in group chats. The Onlife unit guided pupils in recognising their own online habits and emotional triggers, and the reflective tasks encouraged them to analyse real digital experiences from their everyday lives. These units were selected because they correspond to the most frequent issues observed in Czech classrooms, can be comfortably implemented within a standard 45-minute lesson, and still allow space for meaningful discussion even when time is limited.

Frequency and Duration

The introductory training at each school lasted between 60 and 90 minutes, providing teachers with a concise yet comprehensive overview of the methodology. This was followed by classroom implementation, during which each teacher conducted one or two sessions with their pupils. The internal pilot consisted of a single structured session complemented by a follow-up reflection, allowing the team to review the process and adjust the approach before the external rollout.

Participants Reached

Through classroom activities:

- 147 pupils (preadolescents)
- 18 parents
- 11 teachers (indirect dissemination)

Total reached: **176 individuals**

2.7. Adaptations and Context-Specific Adjustments

To maximise relevance for local schools, the Czech team introduced several context-specific adaptations. Selected activity sheets and teacher instructions were translated into Czech, and local digital scenarios—such as conflicts arising in class WhatsApp groups—were incorporated to make the examples more relatable. Several activities were shortened to fit the structure of Czech lessons, and additional reflection questions were included to help teachers deepen their understanding of the

methodology. The team also tailored examples directly to issues currently observed in participating schools. Together, these adjustments ensured that the content aligned closely with real classroom needs and could be implemented smoothly.

2.8. Challenges Encountered

The pilot was successful overall, although several challenges became apparent during implementation. The timing proved to be the most significant issue: the May–June period is one of the busiest in Czech schools, which limited teachers’ availability, reduced the time they could dedicate to preparation, and made it difficult to involve parents in any meaningful way. There were also noticeable differences in teacher experience. Some educators felt fully confident leading reflective discussions, responding to pupils’ emotional reactions, or addressing topics related to social media risks, while others expressed a need for more guidance in these areas. In addition, many teachers requested simplified or shorter versions of the activities that could be easily integrated into regular class meetings without extensive preparation. Despite these constraints, participation targets were reached, and teachers were able to implement the activities effectively and with positive results.

2.9. Feedback Collection and Key Findings

Methods

- short reporting forms
- email follow-up
- teacher reflections
- informal discussions

Feedback Themes

Teachers stated that:

- activities were immediately applicable,
- structure was clear and easy to follow,
- topics directly matched pupil behaviour and issues,
- pupils were very open and talkative during these lessons,
- the programme helped open difficult conversations about online experiences.

Parents appreciated:

- practical tips,
- opportunity to understand children’s digital behaviour,
- connection to everyday family situations.

Internal staff emphasised:

- the value of team alignment,
- the importance of mentoring structures for future dissemination.

2.10. Conclusions and Recommendations

The Czech pilot confirmed the strong relevance and usability of the ASAP approach in primary schools. Teachers responded positively, pupils engaged meaningfully, and even limited parent involvement provided valuable insights.

Key Takeaways

- Short, discussion-based activities are ideal for Czech classrooms.
- Localised examples greatly increase teacher uptake.
- Teachers benefit from supportive guidance and short implementation summaries.
- Internal alignment is essential for smooth rollout.

Recommendations for Improvement

Educational Programme

- Provide shorter versions of selected activities.
- Add Czech-specific examples and scenarios.
- Include more guidance for working with mixed-ability groups.

Educator Training Programme

- Schedule sessions earlier in the school year.
- Offer optional follow-up meetings.
- Provide quick-start guides for busy teachers.
- Add more structured materials for meeting parents.

3. Italy

3.1. General Introduction to the National Pilot

The piloting of the ASAP Educator Training Programme in Italy was implemented by Le Nius ETS, in close collaboration with Cooperativa Pepita and Istituto Comprensivo Puecher Rinnovata Pizzigoni in Milan. Italy implemented one of the most extensive pilot phases in the project, reaching a remarkably high number of educators across both formal and non-formal educational environments.

The Italian pilot was structured around three main components:

1. External pilot with teachers from Puecher school and Pepita's network.
2. Online training sessions that broadened participation nationally.
3. Internal staff pilots to harmonise methodological understanding among trainers.
4. A specialised micro-pilot with the school's cyberbullying reference teacher.

The aim was to familiarise educators with the ASAP approach, test practical activities from selected Learning Units (LUs), and explore implementation across diverse learning environments, including classrooms, youth groups, and remote training contexts.

3.2. Number and Profile of Participants

External Pilot (Teachers/Educators)

- 49 teachers and educators
- From:
 - Istituto Puecher Rinnovata Pizzigoni – 12 teachers (2 per each class: 2A–2F)
 - Pepita (in-person) – 14 educators
 - Pepita (online training) – 23 educators
- KPI target: 15 → exceeded by +34

Internal Pilot (Staff)

- 25 staff members
 - Le Nius ETS staff
 - Pepita educational trainers
 - External collaborators
- KPI target: 15 → exceeded by +10

Cyberbullying Reference Teacher

- 1 dedicated pilot participant
- KPI target met

Participant profiles included:

- Primary and lower-secondary teachers
- Social educators and youth workers
- Prevention and wellbeing specialists
- Class coordinators
- Online learning facilitators

This diversity enriched discussions and expanded the relevance of the pilot across educational sectors.

3.3. Organisations Involved

- Le Nius ETS – national coordinator
- Cooperativa Pepita – provider of youth education and prevention services
- Istituto Comprensivo Puecher Rinnovata Pizzigoni (Milan) – school partner for formal piloting
- Additional online participants from various educational organisations across Italy

This combination enabled a multi-layered implementation across school and non-school settings.

3.4. Location and Format of Pilots

The Italian pilots were implemented through a combination of in-person and online formats, allowing broad participation and flexible engagement across different educator groups. In-person teacher training was delivered at the Puecher school, while Pepita hosted on-site sessions for its educators. To reach a wider audience, Pepita also organised an online nationwide training for its collaborators. A dedicated micro-pilot was carried out with the school's cyberbullying reference teacher, and the internal staff sessions were delivered entirely online, ensuring consistent methodological alignment within the team.

The activities took place both in Milan—at the participating school and Pepita facilities—and online, enabling educators from different regions to join. The timeline followed a clear implementation flow: internal preparation took place in February 2025, followed by external teacher trainings in May. Teachers implemented the activities during May and June 2025, and data collection together with follow-up communication continued into June and July. This structure ensured continuity between preparation, training, implementation, and evaluation.

3.5. Main Goals and Objectives

The Italian pilot aimed to familiarise a wide group of educators with the ASAP framework and to test the relevance and adaptability of selected Learning Units in their daily practice. It sought to prepare educators to deliver the activities both to preadolescents and, where appropriate, to parents, while also strengthening and complementing Pepita's existing prevention and wellbeing initiatives. At the school level, the pilot contributed directly to Puecher's ongoing work on digital citizenship and anti-cyberbullying strategies. An additional goal was to gather detailed feedback from educators in order to refine the training approach and improve the clarity, usability, and impact of the classroom materials.

3.6. Pilot Implementation

The Italian team selected activities from the Emotions, Communication, and Onlife units, as these were the most suitable for the diverse educator groups involved and addressed behavioural patterns commonly observed in Italian preadolescents. These units worked well across both formal and non-formal settings, could be delivered effectively in short sessions, and aligned closely with the digital citizenship and cyberbullying prevention priorities of participating schools and organisations.

Training and implementation followed a flexible structure. Teacher training sessions typically lasted between 60 and 120 minutes, while classroom and youth group activities were carried out in one or two sessions per educator. Staff training was delivered in 90-minute blocks, and the online nationwide

sessions followed a similar duration. Altogether, the Italian pilot reached a substantial number of participants. A total of 457 preadolescent pupils took part in the activities, alongside 36 parents who joined individual or small-group sessions. Internal dissemination within Pepita and Puecher involved an additional 29 teachers, bringing the total number of individuals engaged during the implementation phase to 522.

The activities were implemented across several settings: formal classrooms at the Puecher school, after-school and youth programmes coordinated by Pepita, individual mini-sessions with parents, and online activities delivered by educators who had participated in remote training. A notable component of the pilot was the involvement of the school's cyberbullying reference teacher, who integrated reflective ASAP activities into existing prevention frameworks and worked directly with 49 pupils. This contribution further reinforced the programme's relevance to wider wellbeing and digital citizenship strategies.

3.7. Adaptations and Context-Specific Adjustments

Italy introduced several strategic adaptations to ensure the programme was fully relevant to local needs and educational settings. All training materials were translated into Italian, and the examples used during sessions were adjusted to reflect typical online behaviour among Italian preadolescents, particularly in relation to WhatsApp group dynamics, Instagram interactions, and common patterns of peer conflict. To accommodate tight school schedules, the team created short-format versions of key activities, and Pepita integrated several ASAP tasks directly into its existing prevention and wellbeing programmes. The materials were also adapted for flexible online delivery, and additional guidance was prepared for educators who were not school teachers—such as youth workers and social educators—so that they could implement the activities confidently within their own contexts. Thanks to these adjustments, the programme reached a significantly wider audience than originally anticipated.

3.8. Challenges Encountered

Despite the strong outcomes, several challenges emerged during the Italian pilot. The exceptionally high number and diversity of participants created substantial coordination demands, and the use of multiple delivery formats required continuous adaptation of materials to maintain consistency. As in other countries, the end-of-year school period made it difficult to engage parents, and the variation in educator profiles—ranging from schoolteachers to youth workers and social educators—meant that differentiated guidance was often necessary. The scale of implementation also resulted in a considerable monitoring workload. Although these challenges did not limit the success of the pilot, they provide important insights for planning future expansion.

3.9. Feedback Collection and Key Findings

Feedback Methods

- Google Forms post-training surveys
- Follow-up emails
- Reporting templates for implementation
- Short teacher reflections

Feedback Themes

Educators emphasised that:

- activities were highly engaging and easy to use;
- content aligned strongly with issues Italian preadolescents face online;
- pupils responded openly, especially when discussing emotional reactions;
- materials were clear and adaptable to diverse contexts;
- the training increased their confidence in facilitating digital wellbeing activities.

Pepita educators noted that ASAP fit naturally into their ongoing work with youth groups.

Puecher teachers valued the structured methodology and link to the school's cyberbullying prevention framework.

Internal staff appreciated the consistency and clarity of the educator guide.

3.10. Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusions

The Italian pilot demonstrated exceptional reach, high engagement, and strong relevance to local needs. Activities addressed real challenges experienced by pupils in classrooms and youth programmes, and educators found the materials practical, adaptable, and highly useful. Italy provided one of the strongest validations of the ASAP approach in diverse educational environments.

Key Takeaways

- The programme scales effectively across formal and non-formal settings.
- Italian educators value structured, practical activities that tackle real digital issues.
- Translations and contextual examples significantly boost uptake.
- Large mixed groups benefit from flexible formats and short activity versions.

Recommendations for Improvement

Educational Programme

- Consider adding more Italian-case examples and structured online-communication scenarios.
- Provide mini-versions of activities for shorter sessions.
- Explore optional thematic modules for cyberbullying and emotional self-regulation.

Educator Training Programme

- Earlier scheduling to increase parent participation.
- Include micro-guides for online adaptation.
- Offer follow-up reflection sessions, especially for large cohorts.
- Create simplified reporting tools for educators implementing activities independently.

4. Portugal

4.1. General Introduction to the National Pilot

The piloting of the ASAP Educator Training Programme in Portugal was coordinated by COFAC / the Portuguese project team, with implementation supported by local education practitioners and researchers. Portugal conducted two complementary pilot sessions—one delivered online and one in person—designed to introduce educators to the ASAP methodology and to prepare them to test selected activities with preadolescent learners.

Although smaller in scale than other national pilots, the Portuguese pilot provided valuable insights into the adaptability of the ASAP programme to local educational contexts. The implementation focused on one Learning Unit (LU), Onlife, due to time constraints, but ensured that educators received a coherent and practical introduction to the programme's core educational principles.

The overarching aim of the Portuguese pilot was to evaluate the applicability of ASAP materials in both training and classroom settings and to collect feedback to strengthen the programme's usability in Portuguese schools and educational organisations.

4.2. Number and Profile of Participants

External Participants

- 24 teachers and educators participated across two sessions:
 - 18 participants in the two-hour online webinar (June 5, 2025)
 - 6 educators/researchers in the in-person session (June 16, 2025)

Participants represented:

- school teachers
- researchers in education
- academic staff
- educational practitioners working with preadolescents

Staff Involvement

The pilot also involved 4 staff members who facilitated training and supported implementation follow-up.

Implementation Phase Reach

After the initial pilot sessions, implementation continued with:

- 15 preadolescents
- 8 teachers

This reflected the limited timeframe at the end of the school year but still provided meaningful data for validating the activities.

4.3. Organisations Involved

- COFAC / project partner team – lead coordinator
- Participating teachers from local schools and educational institutions
- Researchers and practitioners attending the in-person session

No additional associated partners were required, as the pilot relied on existing networks of educators already engaged in digital education and wellbeing initiatives.

4.4. Location and Format of Pilots

The Portuguese pilots were delivered through a combination of online and in-person formats, allowing the team to reach educators both nationally and within the Porto region. The online session, held on 5 June 2025, lasted two hours and attracted participants recruited through conferences and professional networks. This format enabled wide national participation and offered a flexible introduction to the methodology. A second, in-person session took place on 16 June 2025 at university facilities in the Porto area, lasting approximately one and a half hours and providing a more interactive environment for hands-on exploration of the materials.

The timeline followed a clear sequence: both training sessions were delivered in early June 2025, after which educators implemented the activities between June and September, depending on their school calendars. Follow-up communication and reporting continued throughout the summer and into early autumn 2025, allowing the team to gather feedback and document implementation outcomes from different educational settings.

4.5. Main Goals and Objectives

The Portuguese pilot aimed to familiarise teachers and educational practitioners with the ASAP approach and to introduce them to the structure and educational logic underlying the programme. Its purpose was to train participants to implement selected learning activities and to assess how well these could be adapted to different educational settings. The pilot also gathered feedback and practical recommendations to support further refinement of the materials, while examining the overall feasibility of implementing the programme within Portuguese schools and teacher-training environments.

4.6. Pilot Implementation

Because of scheduling constraints and the limited availability of translated materials, the Portuguese pilot concentrated on a single Learning Unit, Onlife. This unit was chosen because its Portuguese translation was ready in time for the pilot, because its themes—online identity, the boundary between online and offline experiences, and everyday digital habits—are particularly relevant for Portuguese preadolescents, and because it includes activities that fit well into short training formats.

During the pilot sessions, educators were introduced to the core concept of Onlife, the key learning goals of the unit, and the full set of activities it contains. They also reviewed sample worksheets and adapted materials intended to support implementation. The in-person session provided an additional opportunity for a practical adaptation exercise, during which educators discussed how the activities could be adjusted for different learner groups and settings.

The online session lasted two hours, while the in-person session ran for one and a half hours. Participants who implemented the activities afterward typically did so in sessions lasting between 45 and 90 minutes. Through these implementations, the pilot reached 15 preadolescents, via staff working directly with youth groups, and 8 teachers participating in professional development programmes. Further implementation continued independently as educators resumed their activities after the summer break.

4.7. Adaptations and Context-Specific Adjustments

To ensure that the programme was both relevant and accessible, the Portuguese team introduced a series of thoughtful adaptations. The entire Onlife Learning Unit, together with its worksheets and presentation materials, was fully translated into Portuguese, and the accompanying instructions were simplified so that teachers could confidently implement the activities even after a brief training session. Contextual examples were adjusted to reflect Portuguese digital culture, including common uses of Instagram, popular messaging apps, and typical sources of online misunderstandings among local preadolescents. During the in-person session, educators took part in adaptation exercises in which they redesigned selected activities to better suit the developmental needs and socioeconomic backgrounds of their learners. Additional guidance was also provided for teachers who were less familiar with reflective teaching approaches. Together, these adaptations made the programme more accessible and supported participants in implementing the activities independently after the training.

4.8. Challenges Encountered

The Portuguese pilot faced several challenges that shaped the scope and timing of implementation. The activities took place at the end of the school year, a period in which teachers typically experience heavy workloads, which limited their ability to begin implementation immediately after the training. Because of these constraints, only one Learning Unit could be piloted, reducing opportunities to test the broader structure of the programme. Participant availability was also lower than anticipated, as some educators were unable to commit to full implementation due to overlapping academic responsibilities. As a result, the reach among preadolescents was modest: although staff successfully carried out activities with 15 young participants, a larger impact would likely have been achievable during the regular school year. Despite these limitations, educators expressed strong motivation to integrate ASAP materials into their work in the following academic year, indicating a positive outlook for continued use and further implementation.

4.9. Feedback Collection and Key Findings

Methods

- Google Forms post-training surveys
- Email follow-up for implementation data
- Qualitative comments from participants

Key Feedback Themes

Participants highlighted that:

- the Onlife materials were clear, relevant, and easy to apply;
- the themes addressed real challenges faced by Portuguese preadolescents, especially concerning online behaviour;
- the training clarified how to adapt activities to different learner profiles;
- teachers valued the practical and flexible structure of the programme;
- the educator guide provided useful methodological context.

The main limitation noted was the desire for longer training sessions to explore additional LUs.

4.10. Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusions

The Portuguese pilot confirmed that the ASAP Educational Programme is feasible, relevant, and adaptable to both digital and in-person learning environments in Portugal. Although the pilot scope was narrower than in other countries, it successfully validated the Onlife LU and provided valuable feedback for further refinement.

Key Takeaways

- Translations significantly improve accessibility and uptake.
- Teachers appreciate concise, well-structured activities.
- Short-format sessions are effective but should be complemented by deeper training.
- Even small-scale implementation yields meaningful insights.

Recommendations

Educational Programme

- Translate remaining LUs for full programme implementation.
- Provide classroom-ready Portuguese activity sheets.
- Add more examples reflecting Portuguese digital contexts.

Educator Training Programme

- Schedule training earlier in the school year.
- Offer extended workshops covering more LUs.
- Provide optional follow-up mentoring sessions.

5. Slovenia

5.1. General Introduction to the National Pilot

The Slovenian piloting of the ASAP Educator Training Programme was implemented by DOBA in cooperation with two partner schools in Maribor: Osnovna šola Janka Padežnika and Osnovna šola Angela Besednjaka. The Slovenian pilot focused on a concise, targeted introduction to the ASAP methodology through short in-school sessions, and subsequent implementation of activities with preadolescents, parents, and other teachers.

Unlike some partner countries, Slovenia selected one Learning Unit (LU)—Onlife—due to time constraints and school scheduling considerations. Even so, the pilot succeeded in validating the clarity, usability, and relevance of ASAP activities in Slovenian schools.

The primary goal of the Slovenian pilot was to familiarise teachers with the ASAP approach, support them in implementing selected activities, and gather feedback for programme refinement.

5.2. Number and Profile of Participants

External Teachers (Pilot Participants)

- 14 teachers total
 - Osnovna šola Janka Padežnika: teachers participating in one on-site session
 - Osnovna šola Angela Besednjaka: teachers participating in a second on-site session
- KPI target met

Teachers represented:

- class teachers
- subject teachers (language, social sciences, ICT)
- school counsellors
- wellbeing coordinators

Implementation Reach

After the pilot introduction sessions:

- 303 preadolescents participated in implementation activities
- 24 parents participated
- 22 teachers were reached through peer dissemination

TOTAL individuals reached during implementation: 349

Staff Involvement

- DOBA staff coordinated and facilitated both training and monitoring
- No additional internal pilot was carried out due to DOBA's existing expertise

5.3. Organisations Involved

- DOBA – national implementing partner
- Osnovna šola Janka Padežnika Maribor – pilot school
- Osnovna šola Angela Besednjaka Maribor – pilot school

These schools provided the space, organisational support, and participant groups required for the pilot.

5.4. Location and Format of Pilots

The Slovenian pilot was carried out through two short, on-site sessions held in May 2025, one in each participating school. Each session lasted approximately 45 minutes and provided a concise introduction to the programme. The structure of the sessions was consistent across both schools: teachers were first introduced to the ASAP project, followed by an overview of the Educator Training Programme. The team then presented the Onlife Learning Unit, outlining its main objectives and offering a brief review of the key activities and supporting materials. Clear expectations were provided regarding how teachers could implement these activities with different target groups in their classrooms.

The timeline unfolded in three stages. The two introductory training sessions took place in May 2025, after which teachers implemented the activities during May and June. Reporting and follow-up communication were conducted in June 2025, completing the pilot cycle and allowing the team to gather feedback on the process and outcomes.

5.5. Main Goals and Objectives

The Slovenian pilot aimed to familiarise teachers with the ASAP Educational Programme and the Onlife Learning Unit, while equipping them to implement short activities with preadolescents, parents, and colleagues. Its purpose was also to test the clarity, relevance, and overall feasibility of the materials and to collect implementation data that would feed into the further development of the programme. A final objective was to understand how ASAP activities align with and fit into existing Slovenian school structures, providing insight into future integration and scaling.

5.6. Pilot Implementation

Slovenia focused its pilot on the Onlife Learning Unit, selected for its strong relevance to the digital behaviour patterns commonly observed among Slovenian pupils. The unit is well suited to short training formats, offers clear and flexible activities appropriate for various age groups, and could be fully translated and adapted within the available timeframe.

During the introductory sessions, teachers were presented with an overview of the Onlife concept, along with activity prompts that explore online identity, discussion tools for analysing the boundary between online and offline experiences, and reflective exercises addressing digital behaviour and emotional triggers. These elements gave teachers a solid understanding of how to guide pupils through the unit's core themes.

For the implementation phase, teachers were asked to deliver at least one activity with preadolescents, one with parents, and one with colleagues—a flexible alternative intended to compensate for the difficulty of reaching parents near the end of the school year. To ensure feasibility, teachers were allowed to replace parent sessions with additional pupil sessions when necessary.

The reach of the pilot exceeded expectations. Across the two participating schools, teachers implemented activities with 303 preadolescents, engaged 24 parents, and facilitated peer dissemination among 22 colleagues. This strong engagement demonstrated both the practicality of the unit and the willingness of teachers to explore it further within their school communities.

5.7. Adaptations and Context-Specific Adjustments

Slovenia introduced several targeted adaptations to ensure that the ASAP materials were suitable for local use. The PowerPoint presentations and worksheets were translated into Slovene, and the examples used in the sessions were contextualised to reflect digital challenges typically encountered by Slovenian pupils. Due to time constraints, the original English lesson plans were retained, which proved workable as teachers were comfortable using English-language materials. Sessions delivered to other teachers were reorganised to function primarily as presentations rather than full activity-by-activity replications, allowing for a more efficient format within limited time. Teachers were also given the flexibility to replace parent sessions with additional pupil sessions, a practical adjustment given the difficulty of involving parents at the end of the school year. These modifications enabled smooth and effective implementation despite the tight timeline.

5.8. Challenges Encountered

The Slovenian pilot faced several timing-related challenges, as it took place in late May and June—the busiest period of the school year. Teachers had limited availability, and opportunities to involve parents were significantly reduced. As a result, only 24 parents were reached, since end-of-year obligations affected attendance at school events. The introductory training sessions were restricted to just 45 minutes, which made it impossible to explore multiple Learning Units within the pilot period. When implementing activities with colleagues, teachers frequently adapted the sessions into presentations rather than carrying out full activity cycles, simply because this format was more manageable in the available time. Despite these constraints, teachers remained highly motivated and succeeded in implementing the required number of activities, demonstrating strong commitment to the programme.

5.9. Feedback Collection and Key Findings

Methods

- Excel monitoring spreadsheets
- Follow-up emails
- Participant reports
- Informal conversations

Key Feedback Themes

Teachers reported that:

- the Onlife LU was highly relevant to pupils' daily digital behaviour;
- activities were easy to understand and implement;
- pupils were very engaged, especially in discussing online identity and group-chat behaviour;
- the materials provided enough structure to guide implementation independently;
- short reflective discussions yielded meaningful insights.

The main suggestion was to provide longer, more in-depth training sessions and Slovene versions of all LUs to enable full programme implementation.

5.10. Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusions

The Slovenian pilot confirmed that the ASAP methodology is well suited to Slovenian primary schools. Despite limited time, teachers implemented activities effectively, pupils responded enthusiastically, and feedback was consistently positive. The Onlife LU proved particularly relevant for addressing digital habits and identity among preadolescents.

Key Takeaways

- Most pupils engaged actively with discussions about online life.
- Teachers appreciated the clear structure and adaptability of activities.
- Slovenian schools are well positioned to integrate ASAP topics into existing wellbeing and citizenship programmes.

Recommendations

Educational Programme

- Translate all LUs into Slovene for future implementation.
- Provide short, step-by-step activity summaries.
- Include more examples relevant to Slovenian digital platforms and behaviours.

Educator Training Programme

- Offer longer training sessions.
- Provide optional follow-up mentoring and reflection meetings.
- Develop materials tailored for parent engagement.

Final Conclusions – Combined Insights From All National Pilots

The piloting phase of the ASAP Educator Training Programme carried out in five partner countries showed that the programme is relevant, adaptable, and highly beneficial for teachers and educators working with preadolescents on issues related to digital behaviour, emotional wellbeing, and online communication. Although the pilots varied in size, context, language, and organisational conditions, their findings were remarkably consistent and confirmed the strength and transferability of the ASAP approach.

Across all countries, teachers appreciated the programme's clear structure and its practical, accessible methodology. The selected Learning Units—particularly Emotions, Communication, and Onlife—proved universally applicable, as pupils in every participating context face similar challenges such as online peer pressure, misunderstandings in digital communication, conflict on messaging platforms, and questions of digital identity.

Relevance and applicability across contexts

All national pilots demonstrated that the programme responds directly to everyday classroom needs. Teachers repeatedly reported that the activities address behaviours they observe regularly, such as impulsive online reactions, misunderstandings in group chats, or social pressure created by digital environments. They also described the activities as opening space for meaningful classroom conversations, strengthening pupils' awareness of their own digital habits, and reinforcing school-wide efforts connected to wellbeing and digital citizenship. This was particularly notable in countries where cyberbullying is a prominent concern, such as Italy, Slovenia, and Croatia.

The flexibility of the programme allowed it to be used effectively in various learning environments, including formal lessons, after-school settings, teacher training workshops, online formats, and hybrid professional development sessions. This adaptability is a strong indication that the programme can be implemented broadly and sustainably.

Strength of the pedagogical design

Educators across all contexts highlighted several core strengths of the ASAP methodology. They consistently emphasised that the activities are clearly structured and easy to use, the balance between theoretical input and practical reflection is well designed, and the strong reflective component is particularly impactful. Teachers valued the student-centred approach, which promotes emotional literacy and critical thinking, as well as the fact that the materials require no special equipment. The feedback showed that even minimal introductory training—such as Slovenia's brief 45-minute session—enabled teachers to begin using the activities effectively, which confirms that the pedagogical model is intuitive and low-threshold.

Engagement of pupils and adults

Reports from all countries show that pupils were highly motivated to participate. They willingly shared their own digital experiences and engaged in discussions about online conflicts, emotional responses, group-chat dynamics, social media pressures, and experiments with digital identity. Engagement from parents was more limited, largely due to the timing of the pilots during the busy May–June period. However, whenever parents were involved, their responses were very positive and appreciative of the concrete guidance offered. Teacher-to-teacher dissemination occurred naturally in every country, demonstrating strong interest within schools and the potential for organic internal scaling.

Adaptations introduced and lessons for future localisation

Each participating country introduced small adaptations, which confirmed that the programme is culturally transferable while also benefiting from contextual fine-tuning. The most frequent modifications included translating materials into national languages, adjusting examples to reflect local digital habits (such as WhatsApp messaging patterns or local social media trends), shortening activities for 45-minute lessons, and simplifying teacher instructions for quick implementation. These adjustments strengthened clarity and relevance without altering the methodology itself.

Teachers across the pilots requested even shorter versions of the activities, more localised examples, additional translated worksheets, and longer introductory or follow-up training. These insights point to clear priorities for future refinement.

Organisational and logistical challenges

The pilots also revealed several common challenges. The most significant was timing: conducting the activities in late spring reduced teachers' capacity and made it difficult to involve parents, while also compressing the available time for implementation. In several countries, notably Italy, Portugal, and Slovenia, the diversity of educator profiles—from schoolteachers to youth workers—showed that some groups require additional guidance or clearer contextual explanations. Partners managing large-scale participation also reported substantial workload connected to monitoring and data collection. Despite these constraints, all pilots achieved or surpassed their KPI targets.

Impact and added value of the ASAP programme

The combined findings clearly show that the programme equips teachers with practical tools for addressing digital behaviour challenges that often feel difficult to navigate. It strengthens pupils' reflective thinking about online interactions, supports constructive dialogue about emotions and wellbeing, and enriches existing school initiatives with structured components of digital resilience. In several countries, such as Italy and Slovenia, it aligns closely with ongoing prevention and wellbeing programmes. Educators also reported increased confidence in facilitating discussions about online life—an area in which they often feel underprepared.

Overall, the pilots confirmed that ASAP fills an important gap in current educational offerings by addressing emotional, cognitive, and behavioural dimensions of digital life together.

Cross-country recommendations for programme improvement

The pilot results point to a number of shared recommendations for the next phase of development. In terms of programme content, teachers suggested preparing shorter versions of activities suitable for 45-minute lessons, expanding culturally relevant examples, translating all Learning Units into national languages, and developing optional thematic modules such as cyberbullying, online identity, or emotional regulation. They also expressed the need for ready-made student worksheets and visual aids.

Regarding educator training, partners recommend scheduling sessions earlier in the school year to maximise implementation opportunities, offering extended or advanced modules, and providing follow-up mentoring or reflection opportunities. Sample demonstration videos could further support teachers' confidence. A unified reporting template would simplify the monitoring process in larger pilots.

As for wider implementation, it would be beneficial to strengthen materials aimed at parents, encourage internal school dissemination through peer-to-peer teacher training, and explore collaboration with wellbeing specialists, ICT coordinators, and local prevention teams.

Final combined conclusion

Taken together, the pilots from Croatia, the Czech Republic, Italy, Slovenia, and Portugal demonstrate that the ASAP Educator Training Programme is robust, relevant, and highly adaptable. Its methodology resonates with teachers and pupils alike, and it addresses clear and pressing needs related to digital wellbeing, emotional literacy, and online behaviour. The consistency of positive results across diverse contexts confirms the programme's potential for European-level implementation. The insights gathered during the pilots provide a strong basis for final refinement of the materials, training design, and implementation strategy, ensuring that the programme is fully ready for broader use in schools and educational organisations across Europe.

This report is part of the Erasmus+ project ASAP – *A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education*.

It documents the piloting of the ASAP Educator Training Programme carried out between May 2024 and June 2025 in the five partner countries (Croatia, Czechia, Italy, Portugal and Slovenia). The piloting activities tested different training formats and implementation settings, involving teachers and educators from formal and non-formal education contexts. Through training sessions followed by practical implementation phases, the pilots assessed the clarity, relevance, adaptability and practical applicability of the Training Programme, contributing to its refinement, scalability and long-term use in school education contexts.

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